

Milestone report MS8

Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers

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1. Executive Summary

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability between TREs by development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. The project is supported by four driver projects (hereafter Drivers), i.e. use cases which are prototypic for federated, multinational use of TREs in research practice across scientific domains and user communities:

- **Federated Human Genomics** as a catalyst for European TRE provision (EMBL, CRG, BSC, CSC)
- Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of **administrative and social science data** (CESSDA, GESIS, UKDS, TARKI)
- Enabling the re-use of **clinical trials data** for research purposes across Europe (ECRIN, UiO, HDR UK, UNIVDUN)
- **Public-Private interactions** between TRE in health and environmental data (Turku UAS, CSC, Sigma2)

The Drivers (united in WP7/8/9) both inform and validate the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and provide user input to TRE providers by stating their requirements for TREs.

This milestone report presents the results of a series of workshops (“*Show-and-Tell-sessions*”) organised by the Drivers in May and June of 2025 and concluded with a summary session to define common requirements and challenges for federated data access across Trusted Research Environments (TREs). The results of this workshop series and offline work include:

- an **overview of the Drivers’ prototypes** that are being developed to validate the Blueprint and develop requirements;
- an **analysis** comparing the prototypes to the Drivers’ generic user journey and assessing federation models;
- an **updated and refined set of requirements** based on the workshop discussions and analyses.

This Milestone contributes to the overall project objectives by describing requirements and challenges for federated data access in TREs based on real-world use cases. These will be used by the WP14 to update and extend the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and by WP17 to validate and refine the AAAI architecture. Furthermore, TRE Providers, united in WP11, will use the updated requirements to assess community needs. The updated requirements also form a basis for the further development of the requirements management framework by WP11. Lastly, the prototype of Driver 1 provides a real-world validator of the federated workflow processing technology developed in WP20.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

The MS8 milestone report on drivers baseline requirements has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No. and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP4, WP5)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP2, WP3)	Yes
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP2) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP2, WP5)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP6)	Yes
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP6)	Yes
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP4, WP5).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP4)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP5)	Yes
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP4).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures	No

<p>framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.</p>	<p>for TREs to support the Five Safes¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP5)</p>	
	<p>5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC-compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP4, WP5).</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP4, WP5).</p>	<p>Yes</p>
	<p>2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP2, WP4) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP3).</p>	<p>Yes</p>
	<p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1, WP2).</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1, WP2).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP2).</p>	<p>No</p>
	<p>3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP4).</p>	<p>No</p>

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP3)	Yes
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Abbreviations

AAAI	Authentication, Authorisation, Auditing and Accounting Infrastructure
BAM	Binary Alignment Map, file format for raw genome sequencing data
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center
CDISC	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
crDSR	clinical research Data Sharing Repository
CRG	Centre for Genomic Regulation
CSC	IT Center for Science, TRE provider located in Finland
D	Deliverable
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
EMBL-EBI	EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute
FEGA	Federated European Genome-Phenome Archive
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, TRE provider located in Germany
HDR UK	Health Data Research UK, UK national institute for health data science
HIC	Health Informatics Centre, TRE provider at University of Dundee, UK
ICD-10	International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision
IPD	Individual Participant Data
MedDRA	Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities

MS	Milestone
NHS	National Health Service
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PI	Principal Investigator
RCT	Randomized Controlled Trial
RWD	Real World Data
SANE	Secure ANalysis Environment
SATRE	Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments
SDC	Statistical Disclosure Control
Sigma2	Service provider for national e-infrastructure in Norway
SOPs	Standard Operating Procedures
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
SSO	Single Sign On
TARKI	TÁRKI Social Research Institute, applied social research centre located in Hungary
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
TSD	Services for Sensitive Data, TRE provider at UiO, Norway
Turku UAS	Turku University of Applied Sciences
UiO	University of Oslo
UKDS	UK Data Service, TRE provider located in the UK
UNIVDUN	University of Dundee, UK
WP	Work Package

3. Methods

3.1 Approach for refining and aligning Driver requirements

This EOSC-ENTRUST milestone report summarises the refined requirements gathered from the Drivers and builds upon the requirements defined in MS7 milestone report² and Deliverable 7.1³, where the four Drivers outlined their requirements. The following steps, outlined in paragraphs 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3, have been taken by the Drivers to further refine their requirements:

- **Refinement in show-and-tell sessions:** Each Driver has hosted an online show-and-tell session, where the plans for a prototype (a pilot installation of a real-world use case implemented on one or more existing TREs), challenges, and requirements were discussed and a common understanding between Drivers was sought.
- **Harmonization between Drivers:** A summary session was organized to address and harmonize cross-driver challenges, as well as address and harmonize terminology across Drivers.
- **Restructuring based on Blueprint:** Requirements were mapped on the first version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint⁴. Organizing requirements by capability from the Blueprint enables harmonization, while also retaining Driver-specific requirements.

An overview of the refined requirements can be found in the updated requirements table⁵. These requirements serve as input for the project's providers forum (WP11), the ENTRUST Blueprint (WP14), and the AAAI architecture (WP17).

3.2 Process for challenges and requirements alignment

A two-stage methodology was followed to capture, align, and refine the challenges and requirements of TREs across the drivers. This process consisted of individual “Show and Tell” sessions per Driver, followed by a consolidated “Summary Session.” The approach aimed at harmonising existing gaps and expectations across Drivers and refine them. The

² Anne van der Kant, Jan-Willem Boiten, Milestone report M7.1 Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers [unpublished].

³ van der Kant, A., Boiten, J.-W., Rujano, M. A., Ohmann, C., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Tuikka, A.-M., Wiltshire, D., Casado Barbero, M., Lichtwardt, B., & Bolton, S. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1 Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14988869>

⁴ Sætrom, P., Lehvälaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & Hesam, A. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14362388>

⁵ M8 - Revised driver requirements

sessions also supported the development of a common language, identification of overlaps, and articulation of AAAI needs to inform WP17.

3.2.1 Show-and-tell sessions

Timing: Conducted individually per driver between May and mid-June 2025.

Aim of the sessions: The (online) sessions focused on demonstrating how each driver navigates the process of data access and use within its TRE, while surfacing both technical and procedural requirements. The ultimate aim was to foster harmonization across all drivers and ensure alignment with architectural, governance, and AAAI standards.

Structure:

- Each driver organized its own session, typically lasting between 1–2 hours.
- Sessions were structured around a flexible agenda to include:
 - An introduction to the session and the prototype.
 - A walk-through of the driver’s user journey.
 - A thematic discussion around key elements such as:
 - AAAI expectations for data holders and users.
 - Federation workflows and federated analytics feasibility.
 - Governance structures and their compatibility with federation.
 - Standard Operating Procedures required at both local TRE and federation levels.

Outputs:

- Each session was recorded to ensure accessibility.
- Minutes were documented using a common template highlighting action items, key takeaways, and future steps.
- Drivers were expected to present their critical needs and collect feedback from other WP members to refine requirements

3.2.2 Summary session (aggregation of Drivers’ results)

Date: Held online on **June 23rd, 2025**.

Aim of the session: To consolidate insights, synthesize cross-driver challenges and requirements, and provide actionable recommendations for the TRE framework.

Participants:

- At least one representative from each driver (Drivers 1–4).
- WP representatives from Architecture (WP14), AAAI (WP17), Deployable Demonstrator (WP20), and TRE Providers (WP11).

Structure:

- **Driver presentations** (7 mins each + 3 mins Q&A): Focused on summarizing key takeaways from the Show and Tell sessions, specifically addressing:
 - What is needed in their TREs?
 - What is currently missing or represents a challenge?
- **Cross-driver discussion on the challenges** (40–50 mins): Focused on analyzing overlapping challenges across drivers and identifying concrete action items to address these.
- **Next steps and planning:** Actionable recommendations were defined, with responsibilities assigned to relevant drivers or WPs.

Output:

- Minutes and action points were recorded in a standardized format.
- Harmonized needs and challenges were consolidated to serve as a foundation for further development and refinement of the TRE prototypes by the drivers.

3.3 Drivers’ mappings on generic user journey and federation models

Figure 1: Updated generic user journey for the four Drivers. A minor correction was made for this report, where “Distribute analysis over multiple TREs” is now exclusively shown on the Federation Governance layer.

The generic user journey was first documented in MS7, with an updated version including a federation level published in D7.1. In this milestone report, we have made a minor correction to the generic user journey (see Figure 1). For the current report, the Drivers each mapped their planned prototypes onto this generic user journey to provide an overview of which user journey steps are demonstrated in the Drivers' prototypes and where challenges still arise. It should be noted that the generic user journey was established to connect the current processes that TREs use with the Blueprint. Implementing the Blueprint in EHDS context would shift roles and responsibilities.

In Chapter 4, each Driver also reports the federation model that their prototype will support. The different federation models (Table 1) were previously discussed during both the Driver 3 workshop on IPD metadata analysis and the Blueprint validation workshop organized in Utrecht in January 2025. With the mapping of the Driver prototypes on these federation models, we aim to get a clear view of which models are currently attainable for TREs and which challenges remain on the path to fully remote workflow execution in a federated network (Model 4).

Table 1: Federation models (adapted from Driver 3 presentation)

Model	Analysis Type	Description
1	2-stage	Datasets are analysed in the TRE holding them. The aggregated (and anonymous) results of the individual studies are collected and combined outside of the TREs.
2	Data pooling	Aggregate results from individual studies (analyzed in TREs) are pooled in a TRE within a federated network.
3	Remote execution (simple queries)	A single TRE provides a view of data from multiple studies in the federated network in a virtual table, allowing the researcher to view and interact with the data. The hosting TRE (and project governance) controls what the researcher can and cannot do.
4	Remote execution (complex workflows)	The analysis is executed in one TRE, but it accesses data stored in multiple TREs within the federated network. More advanced than Model 3, allowing complex workflows provided by a third-party service (e.g. Software Service) to be executed on data in multiple TREs.
5	1-stage	Data from multiple data sources are made available and accessible in one TRE. The analysis is performed in this TRE. Data transfer is needed. This might be the only viable option for use cases where data need to be linked on the individual record level before analysis and infrastructure for secure federated linking (i.e. secure multi party computation) is not available.

3.4 Requirements mapping on Blueprint

Drivers' requirements (both existing and newly identified) were mapped on the first version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, in addition to the mapping of the requirements on the SATRE framework⁶, which was done for the first milestone report. To link these two mappings, an additional tab with a mapping between SATRE and the Blueprint was added to the requirements table.

The aim of this mapping is twofold:

1. It allows for grouping of the requirements according to Blueprint capabilities, thus gaining harmonization while also retaining specific requirements that individual Drivers might have.
2. It allows for identifying gaps in both the requirements table and the Blueprint, such that these can be addressed in future discussions.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Driver 1: Federated Human Genomics as a catalyst for European TRE provision

4.1.1 Prototype description

Driver 1's prototype demonstrates federated genomic data analysis workflows across two TREs. Specifically, it addresses **variant calling workflows** applied to **genomic datasets** distributed across TREs.

Figure 2: Driver 1 prototype addressing variant calling over aligned reads (BAM files) in two TREs to identify biomarkers related to Colorectal Cancer

⁶ <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

We showcase compliance with data sovereignty, local governance, and privacy constraints. This prototype emphasizes operational and governance aspects, utilizing:

1. A split **synthetic dataset**. Data obtained from the Federated EGA (FEGA) with granted access to the prototype agent. This single dataset, split in two, corresponds to the data stored in the two TREs (see Figure 2).
2. Pre-approved Variant Calling workflows standardized across TREs.

We aim to prove consistent execution and secure handling of sensitive human genomic data.

Partners in Driver 1 are fully aligned with WP19/20/21 technical demonstrator, for which the latest description can be found in D19.1 deliverable's document⁷.

Figure 3: User journey for Driver 1 prototype

⁷ Quinlan, P., Codó, L., Couldridge, J., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Soiland-Reyes, S., Fernández González, J. M., & Beck, T. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D19.1 Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows Developments. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14412863>

The prototype currently aligns closely with the **"data pooling" model** (model 2), where aggregated results from TREs are pooled within a federated network. For a high-level overview of the main steps of the user journey for the Driver 1 prototype, see Figure 3. Figure 4 shows how the Driver 1 prototype user journey can be mapped onto the more detailed generic user journey.

Figure 4: Driver 1 prototype mapped on the Drivers generic user journey.

4.1.2 Additional requirements

The following additional functional requirements were identified:

1. Mandatory **standardization and harmonization** of genomic datasets prior to analysis.
2. Pre-approval of **external resources** (e.g., reference data and dependencies) without access to the internet.
3. Federation-wide acceptance of **workflows**.
4. Integration of robust **governance checks** at multiple stages (submission, intermediate result generation, result aggregation) without creating massive bottlenecks.
5. Enhanced **visibility and monitoring** tools for tracking workflow execution status and resource utilization within the federated environment.

6. AAI-Related:
 - a. Clear definition of **subject-related attributes** for granting access (e.g., user affiliation, validated ethics approval).
 - b. Comprehensive **logging and auditing** mechanisms, capturing user actions, resource utilization, and workflow execution metadata.
 - c. Support for **querying and filtering audit logs** through intuitive user interfaces (dashboards, reports, alerts).

4.1.3 Remaining challenges

The primary challenges currently identified include:

1. Legal and regulatory constraints limiting **cross-border sensitive data movement** (including intermediate results), necessitating sophisticated federation models. Especially relevant in our "data pooling" model.
2. **Scalability** concerns due to:
 - a. Manual **output reviews** required for intermediate and final result aggregation.
 - b. Approval of **resources** (e.g., Variant Calling workflows or reference genomes) to be used by the researchers.
 - c. Difficulty automating **data anonymization**, resulting in extensive manual checks to guarantee compliance with privacy standards.
3. Complexity in **standardizing workflows** across diverse technical and jurisdictional TRE environments.
4. Ensuring comprehensive and GDPR-compliant **auditing** across federated TREs, including managing retention and privacy of audit data.

4.2 Driver 2: Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative and social science data

4.2.1 Prototype description

The partners in Driver 2 are from three data services: two have established TREs (UKDS (UK), and GESIS (Germany)) and the third is at the start of planning a TRE (TARKI, Hungary). In Driver 2, uniquely to the other Drivers, the TREs are positioned within data archives. This means the data are owned by the research center/survey team responsible for managing the data collection but held within the GESIS or UKDS data archives. This way, the data owners don't directly make the data available to users - the access is handled by the archives via their TREs.

To develop a suitable prototype, we considered a scenario that is hypothetical in this case but not unusual in practice. We hypothesise that three researchers want to access social media data held by GESIS in Germany. The researchers are based in Germany, the UK, and

Hungary. To access the data, the process is currently as follows. All researchers must complete the application process at GESIS, and following that, all must, in theory, travel to Cologne to access the data via the GESIS Safe Room. There is an existing remote desktop connection to GESIS at the UKDS' Safe Room (set up during the SSHOC project), so the UK researcher could potentially travel to the UKDS Safe Room to access the data from there. However, there is no option for the researcher in Hungary but to travel to Germany.

An important step forward and towards being able to facilitate federated analysis across borders is the ability to move data to a different Secure Environment for the duration and purpose of a research project. This is not possible for any of the Driver 2 partners yet, and so far, unthinkable.

We will pilot the move of data into a third-party secure environment and thus test the potential for federation, as well as ease the practical difficulties of the described current situation and facilitate easier research collaboration. For our pilot prototype, we will be using an existing system, so far available only in the Netherlands, namely the SANE Secure ANalysis Environment⁸ developed by SURF⁹. The SANE system provides a virtual, fully-shielded computing environment for access to sensitive data, and runs on the ISO-27001 certified SURF Research Cloud. SANE is developed by SURF and the partners ODISSEI¹⁰ (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations), [National Library of the Netherlands \(KB\)](#), [Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision \(NISV\)](#), and [CLARIAH](#) (Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities). Two variants of SANE are currently available: 'Tinker' and 'Blind'. With Tinker SANE, the researcher is presented with a virtual desktop to see and manipulate the data. It is not possible to transfer the data outside the Tinker environment. With Blind SANE, the researcher can submit a non-interactive analysis that will be executed using the sensitive data in a controlled environment, and the researcher cannot see the data. The analysis can be either a script or a Docker container. For either variant, researchers can log into the secure SANE network and perform their analysis, irrespective of location.

By using SANE for the Driver 2 prototype, we hope to test/achieve a considerable degree of federation and ease the journey to gaining access to sensitive data held in a different country. We hope to overcome governance and equivalence issues, improve our existing TRE offerings, and make it easier for new TREs to be set up.

Overall, we want to use the prototype system to learn which of the main challenges faced when setting up/using TREs can be eased. For example:

⁸

<https://www.surf.nl/en/themes/research-infrastructure/sane-secure-environment-for-analysing-sensitive-data>

⁹ <https://www.surf.nl/en>

¹⁰ <https://odissei-data.nl/nl/>

- We hope to ease some policy/legal constraints where data transfer across borders has not been an option for secure-access data, and cross-national access has so far only been enabled by remote access between Safe Rooms. While some legal boundaries are in place, the risk appetite of data owners may also be a factor. If so, can the inherent security of the system and a potentially easier journey for data providers help to overcome those?
- Equivalence issues also need to be resolved in terms of access levels, access conditions, and technical requirements. This is crucial for getting different TREs/countries to agree to data sharing. How far will having a central infrastructure help abate concerns?
- Resource constraints are an issue for many organisations; for example, limited funding and/or a scarcity of trained professionals to set up and maintain TREs can be prohibitive.
- How far can adopting a third-party infrastructure help overcome limited resources?

Mapping of the prototype on the user journey

Figure 5 illustrates how the generic Drivers' user journey, developed after the Blueprint Validation Workshop, maps to the process for Driver 2's SANE prototype. The models fit together very well, with only a few differences between them, mostly related to the specifics of the SANE system and arrangements for the prototype testing:

- Since the prototype will involve specific datasets and users, it is not envisaged that metadata or a specific catalogue record will be required at this stage.
- Additional software is unlikely to be requested or installed for the prototype; the current software offered by SANE will be used.
- While the prototype testing will be free of charge, the SANE system has a cost model for researchers under normal circumstances.

One permanent difference in the user journey for Driver 2 is that the TREs used by Driver 2 participants (in common with many TREs across the social science and economic

2.D User journey in Driver 2's SANE Prototype

Figure 5: User journey for Driver 2's SANE prototype

disciplines) do not allow users to upload data themselves; import requests are assessed and uploaded by TRE staff if approved.

Federation Model used

For the prototype, Driver 2 will follow Federation Model 1 or 2, as determined at the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Validation Workshop in Utrecht (January 21-22, 2025). Data from UKDS and GESIS will be analyzed in separate SANE project spaces and aggregated outside the TRE (model 1) or in a third SANE project space (model 2). This does not mean that the use of other Federation Models is ruled out for the future structure, since that will depend on the facilities available and data owners' requirements.

Table 2: Analysis of federation models in Driver 2 SANE prototype

Model	Analysis Type	Description	Drivers Prototypes supporting model
1	2-stage	Analysis in each TRE; only aggregated, anonymised results are combined externally.	This model will not be used for the Driver 2 prototype. However, it may need to be used going forward, depending on data owner requirements.
2	Data pooling	Aggregated results from TREs pooled within a federated network.	It is envisaged that this model will be used for the Driver 2 prototype.
3	Remote execution	TRE displays data from other TREs for limited queries. Data not moved.	Data will be moved to the SANE servers for the Driver 2 prototype, so it is not

	(simple)		envisaged that this model will be used there. However, it may need to be used going forward, depending on facilities and data owner requirements.
4	Remote execution (generic)	One TRE runs analysis using data from multiple TREs via complex queries/workflows.	This facility is available in SANE, but is not likely to be used for the Driver 2 prototype. It is possible this model may be used going forward, depending on data owner requirements.
5	1-stage	All data transferred to one TRE. Full analysis done there.	This model will not be used for the Driver 2 prototype. Since pooling data into an on-site Safe Room (like GE would not solve the problems of researcher travel, it will not be offered going forward unless data owners demand it.

4.2.2 Additional requirements

To fulfil AAAI requirements for Driver 2 TREs, auditing data is required from the system to assess user access, resource usage and specific user actions. It is critical that these can be managed via a user-friendly interface, so that staff can fulfil reporting requirements for legal accreditation and audit. Dashboard facilities, downloadable reports, filters by specific data (or other criteria) and notifications or alerts (for unusual patterns of activity as well as other events) should be built into the system using common terminology, so that it is flexible and easy to use across providers. During the prototype trial, the inbuilt SANE system reporting facilities will be used.

4.2.3 Mapping requirements on partner TRE capabilities

The UKDS and GESIS need control over all objects and workflows in their TREs, including research datasets, metadata fields and workflow definitions. They also need to know all object-related attributes to grant access to objects, including access conditions, data ownership, level of data sensitivity, metadata status, researcher status, project approval, project duration and curation status. The object-related attribute values are governed by the TRE rules, the data owner, legal conditions, and the researcher and project status. Information about the researcher is gathered from the data/project application form, including researcher status, researcher approval, project status and project approval. The TRE makes the requisite checks to verify the information. Neither the UKDS nor GESIS TREs allow data upload by researchers. If a data import is requested, it is loaded into the researcher's project folder by TRE staff once it has been checked and approved. The project status and researcher accreditation must be current. At the UKDS, this is verified from researcher accreditation (training complete and test passed), from project application

approval by the data owner and project status (i.e. the project has been approved by the data owner and has not expired). Training arrangements may differ between the UKDS and GESIS, but object control and workflows are largely the same. TARKI does not yet have a TRE, so procedures and workflows do not yet apply. We do not anticipate significant changes to object control or workflow during the prototype testing period.

UKDS and GESIS have similar capabilities for AAI, and mapping can be done to focus on specific similarities or differences. The UKDS may also have some additional legal reporting needs for certain categories of data under the UK Digital Economy Act. TARKI does not yet have a TRE, and so requirements are yet to be fully determined.

4.2.4 Remaining challenges

While there is a good fit between the user journey and the planned prototype, there are some known challenges which would also be important to consider should the testing phase lead to a permanent system:

- Contracts, agreements and setting up access to the SANE system across the partner TREs may take longer than anticipated.
- One requirement of SANE is that the data will need to be transferred to a server in the Netherlands; not all data owners involved have yet agreed to this.
- Compatibility in output checking procedures between UKDS and GESIS needs to be ensured (TARKI does not yet have a TRE) to overcome any discrepancies.
- Sufficient and timely expert cover must be in place to support users who are unfamiliar with the available software, which could impact TRE resources.

The prototype is small at this stage, and while the Driver 2 team are likely to be able to resolve all issues, a more permanent and larger-scale installation may lead to additional challenges. Our aim with the prototype is to try to explore how infrastructural, governance and legal blocks to the potential development of federated access can be overcome, in our aim to share sensitive administrative and social science data.

4.3 Driver 3: Enabling the re-use of clinical trials data for research purposes across Europe

4.3.1 Prototype description

The Driver 3 prototype is entitled “*Federated analysis of Randomized Controlled Trial and Real-World data across two Trusted Research Environments to compare comorbidities in older adults vaccinated against COVID-19*”.

The objective of the prototype is twofold:

i) To investigate analytical approaches for federating two TREs, operating in two different countries (TSD¹¹ in Norway and HIC¹² in Scotland), for an analysis involving two different data types (Randomized Controlled Trial - RCT and Real World Data - RWD).

ii) To perform an evidence synthesis comparing Individual Participant Data (IPD) from an RCT with RWD filtered by similar inclusion criteria to assess the generalizability of the trial results on comorbidities in elderly individuals vaccinated against COVID-19.

Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)

- *Study:* Assessing Immune Response of Different COVID-19 Vaccines in Older Adults (EU-COVAT-1) (NCT05160766)¹³
- *Data controller:* University of Cologne
- *Data source:* crDSR¹⁴ (TSD TRE in Norway)
- *Population:* 269 participants
- *Metadata:* Documented in crDSR under ¹⁵

Real-World Data (RWD)

- *Data controller:* National Health Service (NHS) Tayside, Scotland
- *Data source:* Vaccination records of the Tayside population stored in HIC TRE in Scotland
- *Population:* 411,643 individuals
- *Metadata:* Documented in Healthdatagateway¹⁶

¹¹ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>

¹² <https://www.dundee.ac.uk/hic>

¹³ Neuhann JM, Stemler J, Carcas AJ, Frías-Iniesta J. et al. Immunogenicity and reactogenicity of a first booster with BNT162b2 or full-dose mRNA-1273: A randomised VACCELERATE trial in adults ≥75 years (EU-COVAT-1). *Vaccine*. 2023;41(48):7166-7175. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2023.10.029.

¹⁴ <https://crdsr.ecriin.org/login>

¹⁵ <https://crdsr.ecriin.org/browsing/studies/DSRS-2/view>

¹⁶ <https://healthdatagateway.org/en/data-custodian/10>

Mapping of the Driver 3 prototype on user journey

Figure 6: Mapping of Driver 3 prototype on generic user journey.

For the user journey mapping shown in Figure 6, the user journey steps discussed during the 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop on 5 and 6 May 2025 are used.

Some clarifications:

- Creating a “Federation Governance” layer is beyond the scope of this prototype, as it would require additional resources, time, and political commitment. Instead, the Driver 3 prototype focuses on exploring how federated analysis between two different TREs can be achieved in the current context, where a “Federation Governance” layer is not yet in place. The aim is to identify practical steps, test feasibility, and report any challenges to EOSC-ENTRUST that should be considered in the Blueprint delivery. The “ticked boxes” in the “Federation Governance” layer (Figure 6) represent the specific elements Driver 3 has identified as essential for future implementation in a federated TRE network.
- For “User Training and Certification” we believe that at this stage this is something likely to be dealt with by each individual TRE rather than the “Federation

Governance". This is because there is still much heterogeneity in how different TREs function and having training delivered at the "*Federation Governance*" layer might not yet be adequate.

- In the Driver 3 prototype, the Data holders have provided data to the TREs at an earlier stage (e.g., upon the completion of the clinical trial), and the TREs act as data custodians.
- In the Driver 3 prototype, "*Data de-identification*" is not performed by the *Data holder*. For both the clinical trial and the RWD, this step is performed by the "*TRE Governance*".
- The "Data holder" is not performing SDC. In the Driver 3 prototype, this step is dealt with by the "*TRE Governance*".

Federation Model

During the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Validation Workshop in Utrecht (January 21-22, 2025), the possible analysis models presented in Table 3 were discussed:

Table 3: Analysis of federation models and how they apply to the Driver 3 prototype

Model no	Analysis type	Description	Driver 3 prototype
1	2-stage	Datasets will be analysed in the TRE holding them. The aggregated (and anonymous) results of the individual studies are collected and combined outside of the TREs.	IPD analysed separately in the TSD TRE and the HIC TRE. Aggregated results combined outside of the TREs.
2	Data pooling	Aggregate results from individual studies (analyzed in TREs) are pooled in a TRE within a federated network.	IPD analysed separately in the TSD TRE and the HIC TRE. Aggregated results combined in one of the two TREs.
3	Remote execution (simple)	A single TRE provides a view of IPD from multiple studies in the federated network, allowing the researcher to view and interact with the data. A virtual table is created from different sources, but full analysis will depend on the capabilities of the presenting tool. It's up to the hosting TRE (and project governance) to decide what the researcher can and can't do. Model 3 is a simpler version of Model 4, and it is useful when remote queries can be easily encapsulated in a single message and datasets are homogeneous and tabular.	TSD and HIC are not part of a federated TRE network. In a theoretical exercise, requirements for Model 3 to be achieved will be collected.
4	Remote execution (generic)	The analysis is executed in one TRE, but it accesses IPD stored in multiple other TREs within the federated network. More advanced than Model 3, allowing	TSD and HIC are not part of a federated TRE network.

		<p>complex multi-study analyses without direct data movement.</p> <p>The main difference between Model 3 and Model 4 comes down to the complexity of the query sent between TREs. Model 3 works with simple queries that can be directly sent from TRE A to TRE B, while Model 4 handles more complex queries that can't be packaged as a simple message. Instead, TRE A asks TRE B to run a specific workflow provided by a third-party service (e.g. Software Service C). Thus Model 4 adds an extra layer by involving a third party to handle complex workflows, while Model 3 relies on straightforward, direct queries.</p>	In a theoretical exercise, requirements for Model 4 to be achieved will be collected.
5	1-stage	<p>IPD of all data sources are available and accessible in one TRE. The analysis will be performed in this TRE. Data transfer(s) are needed.</p>	In a theoretical exercise, requirements for Model 5 to be achieved will be collected.

The Driver 3 partners will discuss with the 2 TREs (TSD, HIC) the feasibility of all 5 models and derive requirements to inform the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. Whenever a model cannot be applied (e.g., due to lack of a pre-existing TRE federation network), requirements to enable the analysis will be collected in a theoretical exercise.

4.3.2 Additional requirements

In the Driver 3 “Show and tell” Meeting report¹⁷, we performed a point-by-point comparison of the current capabilities of the 2 TREs (TSD, HIC) in terms of *Authentication, Authorization & Access Control (AAAI), Federated workflow execution, Output control policy, and Standard Operating Procedures*. In addition, challenges that TSD and HIC see around these topics for an eventual federation governance have been captured.

In brief, what seems to be missing:

- A trust framework for external identity providers
- TRE acceptance framework for externally issued attributes or claims for authorization decisions
- Logging of access decisions across federated systems
- Execution of workflows across multiple TREs without moving data
- Controlling outputs in a federated analysis involving multiple TREs
- SOPs describing how the TRE federation is implemented in the TRE operations

Driver 3 has revised the requirements collection table¹⁸.

¹⁷ [EOSC-ENTRUST Driver 3 “Show and tell” session Meeting report](#), unpublished

¹⁸ [M8 - Revised driver requirements](#)

4.3.3 Remaining challenges

- The 2 TREs in Driver 3 **operate differently** and have **different capabilities**. Differences arise from operating within different geographical contexts (Norway, Scotland) and working with different user communities (TSD rather field-agnostic; HIC focused mainly on RWD from healthcare).
- One key difference between the two TREs is **how output control is managed**. In TSD, the Principal Investigator (PI) has the right to export data and can grant this permission to other project members by assigning them to the export group. The TRE itself does not review the content of exported files. Instead, data handling by the PI and project members is governed by contractual obligations and prior ethical approvals. While this approach works within a single-institution context, it may present challenges in a federated network, particularly for projects involving multiple data controllers or joint controllers. HIC employs a centralised output control process. All outputs are subject to Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC), a rules-based, triaged approach that includes suppression of small cell counts (typically for values of $n < 5$) to reduce the risk of re-identification.
- **Data-related challenges** include differences in terminology and data standards. For example, the RCT has used MedDRA for clinical terminology while RWD employs ICD-10. Similarly, there may be mismatches in data structuring standards, such as CDISC (RCT) versus OMOP (RWD), which can hinder interoperability and complicate federated analysis.
- Federating TREs is a resource-intensive process. Thus, **demonstrating public benefit of and demand for TRE federation** is fundamental. In this process, **data controllers** are key stakeholders and have a big role to play. They remain legally responsible for the processing and use of sensitive data in the TREs. The TREs act as **data processors**. Having a federation in place could be seen as an inconvenience by the usual “TRE clients” (*meaning here data controllers*) and it has proven to be a tricky point for health data, with different boards having different “trust” requirements even within the same country (e.g., Scotland).

4.4 Driver 4: Public-Private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data

4.4.1 Prototype description

Description of the prototype

The Driver 4 prototype aims to design a proof-of-concept for federating two TREs to enable developing machine learning models or used separately to create synthetic data.

The prototype development includes two steps:

- First, the SPE is adapted to enable creating synthetic data based on the sensitive dataset. In this case, the SPE is CSC's SD Services and one of its modules, SD Desktop, is used as a virtual workspace to create synthetic data. SD Desktop is considered secure enough for transferring and analysing the sensitive dataset, thus, the prototype development focuses on its functionalities to enable creating synthetic data.
- Second, a proof-of-concept is designed to represent requirements, workflows and governance practices for creating machine learning models in federated TREs. To define a detailed enough description two specific environments are chosen: CSC's SD Services and the Turku University of Applied Science's environment.

The source data that is used to create the machine learning model is sensitive in nature. We have several data sets. One data set derives from a public-private partnership between Turku University of Applied Science and their long-term partner, a local Sports Academy. The dataset includes personal information about football players representing different age groups (minors, young athletes, adults). Because the dataset is property of the Sports Academy and it has commercial value for them, it is considered sensitive in nature. Athletes have given their consent to use their data for research purposes. Another is image data from medical MRI images.

Federation models

Federation models (Table 4) are interesting from the viewpoint of the Driver 4 prototype because the prototype aims to design a proof-of-concept for federating two TREs to enable developing synthetic data or other machine learning models. Federated learning has the potential to use sensitive homogenous or heterogenous data from many sources to create one robust machine learning model. This is useful in many fields.

Synthetic data is created through machine learning and requires complex algorithms and specific software tools. Multiple data sets are needed for training and testing purposes. If algorithms can be transferred and executed in each TRE locally or within the federation, it is not necessary to move source data used for training or testing purposes between TREs.

However, synthetised data which is created as an outcome of this development needs to be moved between TREs. When synthetic data has met the desired quality, it should be possible for the user to retrieve it from the TRE.

Synthetic data can be seen as aggregated and the goal of creating good quality synthetic data is that it is anonymized. The anonymity and usefulness of synthetic data must be tested before use. Thus, synthetic data has the potential to enable federation models 1 and 2 for different types of research scenarios that currently require access to sensitive data.

Table 4: Federation models in relation to the Driver 4 prototype

Model	Analysis Type	Description	Drivers Prototypes supporting model
1	2-stage	Analysis in each TRE; only aggregated, anonymized results are combined externally.	This model will be used in Driver 4. Synthetic data can be perceived as anonymized data thus fit for enabling this federation model. The challenge is making sure that no sensitive data is exposed when the synthetic data or synthetic data machine learning models are moved out of the TRE.
2	Data pooling	Aggregated results from TREs are pooled within a federated network.	For synthetic data this is relevant in Driver 4 if we can consider anonymous synthetic data to fit this description. Synthetic data can be perceived as aggregated data that could be used for data pooling. For federated learning this is relevant because the parameters of models during training are transferred between TREs. These do not contain sensitive data.
3	Remote execution (simple)	TRE provides access to data from other TREs for limited queries. Data are not moved.	In Driver 4 prototype no access is given to sensitive data to other TREs. Only anonymous data should be able to move.
4	Remote execution (generic)	One TRE runs analysis using data from multiple TREs via complex queries or workflows. More advanced than Model 3, allowing complex multi-study analyses without direct data movement.	This model will not be used in Driver 4 because no sensitive data is moved between TREs. Only anonymous data is moved.
5	1-stage	All data sources are available and accessible in one TRE. Analysis can be	This model will not be used in Driver 4 because no sensitive data is moved

		done completely in one TRE by using data sources available within a federated network.	between TREs. Only anonymous data is moved.
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Mapping of the Driver 4 prototype user journey

In the case of the prototype, the user journey starts with a PI who has access to source data prior to accessing the SPE. The PI can upload the data to SD Services by using SD Connect. Then the data is available in SD Desktop for further analysis. Other members of the research project can use SD Desktop to analyse the data but they cannot download data from SD Desktop. However, the PI can download the data produced or analysed within SD Desktop.

The Driver 4 prototype was mapped in relation to the user journey steps discussed during the 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop on 5 and 6 May 2025 (presented in the Figure 1, section 3 Methods). Figure 7 presents which of these steps are relevant for the Driver 4 prototype with following symbols:

- If the user journey step is relevant for Driver 4 prototype, it is marked with a ✓ symbol.
- If the user journey step is not relevant for Driver 4 prototype, it is marked with X symbol.
- If the user journey step is unclear it is marked with ? symbol.

Identified gaps in the user journey

In the case of the Driver 4 prototype, Sports Academy has entered into an agreement with Turku University of Applied Science to provide a dataset for research purposes. This contract defines Sports Academy as data controller and Turku University of Applied Sciences as data custodian. This contract was made before researchers at Turku University of Applied Sciences started to use the TRE. Researchers also received the dataset before they started to use the TRE. Hence, Data holder is a confusing term to be used for one of the roles in the user journey. It is unclear if it would refer to Sports Academy, which is a data controller, or to Turku University of Applied Sciences. As data custodian, Turku University has access to the dataset and the ability to provide it to the project space in the TRE.

The user journey for the Driver 4 prototype does not include a data request and does include an “upload data” step for the data user. Based on this prototype development, the generic user journey for EOSC-ENTRUST would need to be adapted to allow for data access without a request procedure, since users in this prototype have access to data before they start using a TRE. In these use cases, users need the TRE for data analysis or sharing data between project collaborators, but they don’t need the TRE to access new datasets.

Figure 7: Mapping of the Driver 4 prototype on the user journey steps discussed during the 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements and Capabilities Workshop on 5 and 6 May 2025.

4.4.2 Additional requirements

- In the case of AI development, packages are downloaded from different sources and might not work with each other. Finding the right set of packages is a very time-consuming phase. Thus, the researcher would need **a dynamic user interface** which enables downloading packages on demand.
- **Sufficient resources** are needed especially when multiple people work within the same virtual workspace.
- **Integrated AI tools** (in the TRE) could help researchers to develop the necessary algorithms and solutions more easily and efficiently. They could also be used to analyse the quality of synthetic data.

4.4.3 Remaining challenges

Synthetic data has the potential to facilitate research and development that has previously required the usage of sensitive data. Synthetic data could be shared more widely or

possibly even opened completely to expand the amount of datasets available. Currently multiple challenges are related to broadening the usage of synthetic data.

Reverse engineering

Reverse engineering is a challenge related to AI models and AI-generated datasets, such as synthetic data. Reverse engineering refers to the possibility to recreate training data based on outcomes of the AI development. For example, reverse engineering training data based on synthetic data might be possible if one has access to the AI model, which was used to create synthetic data. For synthetic data there exists methods like differential privacy which is mathematically guaranteed to be privacy preserving even in the case of reverse engineering.

Demand from the private sector

Synthetic data is not yet widely used by organizations in the private sector for their research and development needs. For example, pharma companies have not adopted synthetic data for developing new medications.

5. Results & Discussion

5.1 Prototypes

Table 5 shows an overview of the Drivers' prototypes as described in the current milestone report, including the TRE(s) that the prototypes will use and the federation models that the prototypes support. The overview shows that 2-stage and data pooling models are most prevalent in the prototypes, reflecting the current possibilities in federated data access, mainly restricted by the lack of common standards and governance models that generate enough trust to combine data over TREs.

The Driver's prototypes will demonstrate a variety of federation models, from workflow execution over datasets hosted in multiple TREs to data processing in a single TRE with the aim to generate transferable synthetic data, thus testing federated data access on various levels (the order in which the Drivers are named reflects the level of federation):

- **Driver 4** aims to **generate synthetic data based on sensitive source datasets in a TRE**, thus taking a different approach to keeping data secure by making sensitive data sharable outside TREs. Other federation models will be tested by developing requirements for creating machine learning models from sensitive data in a federation.
- **Driver 2** aims to **transfer data to a third-party secure environment (SANE)**, which serves as the Research Analytics Zone (RAZ, see the first version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint) with remote access capabilities. This allows for

cross-border data access without travel, while the data remain under the control of GESIS.

- **Driver 3** aims to **analyse data in two separate TREs and combine the results**, either in one of the TREs or externally. Other federation models will be explored theoretically.
- **Driver 1** works together with WP19/20/21 to **run a data analysis workflow over two TREs and combine the results in one of the TREs** in an automated way.

The mapping of prototypes on the federation models provided a validation through real-life use cases of the model classification. This gave rise to a discussion and revealed a need for clear definitions of federation models and a classification of levels of federation relative to each other. The Drivers agree that this should be discussed broader among EOSC-ENTRUST WPs, leading to updated and agreed-upon definitions of the models of federation that the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint aims to support.

Table 5: Overview of Driver prototypes, with description, TRE(s) used and the federation model(s) that are demonstrated by each prototype

Driver	Prototype description	TRE(s)	Federation model(s)
1	Cross-national variant calling over aligned reads hosted in two TREs	BSC TRE TRE-FX	2
2	Cross-national social & environmental access to data hosted in GESIS through SANE	SANE GESIS TRE UKDS TRE	1/2
3	Cross-national federated analysis of RCT and RWD across two TREs to compare comorbidities in older adults vaccinated against COVID-19	TSD HIC	1 & 2
4	Developing synthetic data from sensitive source datasets in TRE	SD Services	1 & 2

5.2 User journey mapping

Figure 8 shows a summary of the mappings of the Drivers' prototypes on the generic user journey. This summary shows that the Drivers' prototypes cover the majority of the user journey, with some steps commonly covered by all Drivers, while others are only relevant to two of the Drivers.

Some Drivers also noted that, at least in the prototypes, other actors/roles are responsible for certain steps than shown in the user journey. These differences between Drivers and TREs are complicated to fully harmonize. Therefore, a federation will need to account for differences between TREs in their internal operations, while standardizing the interfaces, like the communication with the *federation governance* layer.

The Drivers' prototypes thus provide a broad demonstration of what is needed for federated data access. This does not mean, however, that full federation is covered in the Drivers' prototypes (challenges to this are discussed in section 5.3.2). Differences in TRE maturity have to be taken into account and the prototypes provide a first step towards federation by providing practical implementations of "mini-federations" that serve to validate the Blueprint architecture.

Figure 8: Mapping of Drivers' prototypes on generic user journey. Numbers indicate the Drivers that have marked a step as relevant for their prototype. Numbers between brackets indicate steps where the relevance to a Driver's prototype is unclear.

5.3 Requirements and challenges

5.3.1 Show-and-tell summary session outcomes

Each of the four drivers presented key findings, followed by a collective discussion aimed at identifying overlaps, divergences, and actionable recommendations.

Drivers showcased diverse use cases ranging from cross-national data sharing and federation of clinical trial and real-world data to synthetic data generation and secure data

access. Common themes emerged around the heterogeneity of TRE processes, the complexity of federating infrastructure, and the challenges of harmonizing governance across nodes. Drivers emphasized that although technical readiness varies, shared goals like data security, transparency, and user enablement drive convergence.

Driver 3 highlighted the need for a project-based federation model and acknowledged significant differences in output control and legal responsibilities across TREs. **Driver 4** underscored the early-stage development of synthetic data workflows and the lack of pharma engagement, calling for more robust evaluation methods. **Driver 2** emphasized gaps in equivalence, role definitions, and user support, while **Driver 1** reflected on the technical setup of EGA nodes and the importance of defining federated access roles clearly.

The cross-driver discussion reinforced the need for pragmatic approaches that acknowledge institutional constraints and evolving trust. It was recognized that the shift from on-site to remote access in some TREs had already helped build confidence across the ecosystem. Architecture, user journey design, and AAI integration were discussed as areas requiring stronger alignment.

5.3.2 Consolidated challenges from summary session

Challenges Identified

- **Varying levels of AAI infrastructure and readiness:** Not feasible for now to have a common AAI infrastructure across TREs due to varying standards and technology being used.
- **Heterogeneous user journeys:** Differences in user flows across TREs make alignment difficult, especially for users embedded in legacy systems.
- **Lack of federated TRE network:** Many TREs still operate in isolation, with limited interoperability mechanisms.
- **No harmonization of legal and technical frameworks:** Policies, governance, and SOPs vary widely, hindering unified operations.
- **Output control and shared workflows:** Absence of common guidelines for federated output validation and responsibilities.
- **Terminology ambiguity:** Roles such as data owner, holder, and provider are inconsistently defined across drivers.

Detailed challenges per driver can be found in appendix 2.

Recommendations

- **Starting small with federation,** since full federation still has a lot of challenges such as, no harmonization of policies, legal and technical frameworks; heterogeneous user journeys and systems across TREs; and many more.

- Develop a **flexible federation framework** rather than enforcing uniformity, allowing for driver-specific use cases.
- Establish a **centralized governance layer** to support coordination while respecting local autonomy.
- Leverage existing models (e.g., DARE-UK, Nordic TRE collaborations) as reference points for harmonization.
- Create common SOPs for output checking, including **training modules** and **reference criteria** for federation-wide use.
- Define role terminology clearly in the context of AAI and update user journeys to reflect federated access requirements.

These outcomes will feed into the refinement of TRE prototypes and the next phase of WP8 alignment under EOSC ENTRUST.

5.3.3 Consolidated up-to-date requirements

The refined and restructured requirements can be found in the revised Driver requirements table¹⁹. This table includes the mapping of the requirements to the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, as described in the *Methods* section. Additionally, newly identified as well as updated requirements have been added to the table and marked with *MS8* in the column *Version*. New requirements were added from the following sources:

- The Drivers' show-and-tell sessions and the work reported in the current Milestone report (see sections 4.1.2, 4.2.2, 4.3.2 and 4.4.2);
- The gap analysis that was performed in the Blueprint Validation Workshop in January 2025 and reported in D7.1, as far as these were not added to the requirements table yet.

6. Conclusion

The Drivers' prototypes collectively illustrate the diverse and evolving landscape of federated data access across Trusted Research Environments (TREs). While the majority of prototypes currently rely on 2-stage and data pooling models, this reflects both the technical feasibility and the limitations imposed by the lack of common standards and unified governance frameworks. The mapping of these prototypes onto the generic user journey reveals substantial coverage, though also highlights operational and role-based discrepancies across TREs. These differences underscore the need for federation models that accommodate local variation while standardizing interfaces and governance interactions.

¹⁹ M8 - Revised driver requirements

The results of the show-and-tell sessions, both the challenges and the resulting additional requirements, further emphasize the complexity of achieving full federation. Key barriers include inconsistent AAI infrastructure, fragmented legal and technical frameworks, and ambiguous role definitions. Nonetheless, the Drivers' work provides a pragmatic foundation for future alignment, offering "mini-federations" as proof-of-concept implementations that inform the next phase of WP8 by posing detailed requirements, both on federation services, federation governance and individual TREs.

Moving forward, the recommendations call for a flexible federation framework, centralized governance support, and clearer role definitions. These steps are essential to foster trust, interoperability, and scalability across the federated ecosystem. The insights gained from the Drivers' prototypes will be instrumental in refining the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. To support TREs in becoming "federation-ready", the Blueprint might be accompanied by a maturity model, which meets the Drivers and Providers where they are and guides them through the next steps towards supporting federated data access.

7. Next steps

The current milestone report will serve as a basis to provide input to the second version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint during the Evaluation & Adoption workshop organised in September 2025 by WP14 (Architecture). During the process of the preparation of the second Blueprint version, the Drivers WP will align the results reported here with the needs of WP14.

During the remainder of the calendar year, the Drivers will further develop their prototypes, the results of which will be reported in the next Deliverable report (February 2026), together with a mapping of the prototypes on the second version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and a gap analysis between the requirements that the prototypes pose and the Blueprint architecture. Because there is a potentially large overlap between the capabilities of the Drivers' prototypes and the capabilities of the TREs on which these prototypes are mounted, alignment will be sought with WP11 (Providers) on the gap analyses reported in the Drivers' and Providers' next deliverables, respectively. For both the gap analysis and the alignment with WP11, a preparatory (online) workshop will be organised after the delivery date of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, second version.

Looking ahead toward the third year of the project, a higher level of alignment will need to be reached to drive adoption of the Blueprint by both Drivers and Providers. The levels of Blueprint adoption by the Drivers and Providers will be reported in the final set of Deliverables. The current Milestone report demonstrates that the current practices differ greatly between TREs. To measure and drive adoption of the Blueprint by both Drivers and Providers, a maturity model for TREs might be beneficial.

Appendix

Overview of drivers, partners, and TREs

Driver	Partners	TREs
Driver 1: Federated Human Genomics as a catalyst for European TRE provision	CSC CRG BSC	SD Services BSC TRE
Driver 2: Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative and social science data	CESSDA GESIS UKDS TARKI	GESIS TRE UKDS
Driver 3: Enabling the re-use of clinical trials data for research purposes across Europe	ECRIN UiO HDR UK UNIVDUN EMBL-EBI	TSD HIC
Driver 4: Public-Private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data	Turku UAS CSC Sigma2	SD Services

Challenges experienced by drivers

Federation & Interoperability

Challenge	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4	Discussion and conclusions
Heterogeneous user journeys and systems across TREs	✓	✓	✓	✓	Centralized government layer; legal layer
Lack of pre-established federated TRE network	✓	✓	✓	✓	Catching up with federation wp; reproducibility for example, check-list; stakeholder agreement and higher level agreements (political will)

No harmonization of policies, legal and technical frameworks	✓	✓	✓	✓	Taking inspiration from already existing frameworks (eg. nordic region, Swiss use-case, FEGA (as an example framework));EHDS should bring up legal framework for health data
Lack of SOPs for federated outputs and combined workflows	✓	✓	✓	✓	A common output checker training/ standards
Federation not aligned with current TRE client expectations	✓		✓		
No clear method to combine outputs from multiple TREs	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Limited federation experience/prior projects	✓	✓	✓		
Differences in data standards and terminology(e.g. MedDRA vs ICD-10)	✓		✓		

AAAI (Authentication, Authorization & Access Infrastructure)

Challenge	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4	Discussion and conclusions
Varying levels of AAAI infrastructure and readiness	✓	✓	✓	✓	Common standards, technology to comply with, Laws to adhere to
Manual or incomplete AAAI processes		✓		✓	
TREs cannot currently trust external Identity Providers (IdPs)	✓	✓	✓	✓	Driver 3: TSD in Norway currently working on this for: eIDAS, Swiss ID, Nordic IdPs.

Federated authorization is seen as the hardest component	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Lack of standard trust frameworks for identities		✓	✓	✓	

Output Control & Data Movement

Challenge	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4	Discussion and conclusions
No uniform output control policies across TREs	✓	✓	✓	✓	First step: transparency on thresholds for SDC per TRE Output checker training
Responsibility for output control varies per TRE	✓	✓	✓	✓	Output checker training
TREs differ in policies on statistical disclosure control	✓		✓	✓	
Export risks remain unmitigated		✓	✓	✓	

Technical Integration

Challenge	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4	Discussion and conclusions
Balancing local TRE systems with federation requirements	✓	✓	✓	✓	
No shared infrastructure for workflow execution	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Lack of support for federated workflows		✓	✓	✓	

Legal, Roles & Governance

Challenge	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4	Discussion and conclusions
Terminology confusion: Data owner vs controller vs holder		✓	✓	✓	Driver 3: There is terminology confusion but as long as the legal roles of data controller and data processor are clear this is not then a major challenge.
Unclear and varying governance roles in federation	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Joint or multiple data controller responsibilities unclear	✓		✓	✓	
Lack of legal clarity for federated projects		✓	✓	✓	

Trust, Adoption & Readiness

Challenge	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4	Discussion and conclusions
Federation seen as too ambitious; project-based federation preferred		✓	✓	✓	
Data controllers' 'trust' thresholds differ even within a country	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Data owner consent and local regulations vary, complicating standardization	✓				
Public benefit and demand for TRE federation not yet demonstrated			✓	✓	